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Jyldyz
URMANBETOVA

Çolpon
NAİMANOVA

İNTOBA

JHSSA

Prof. Dr. Kırgızistan-Türkiye Manas Üniversitesi, Bişkek / Kırgızistan
cildiz.urmanbetova@manas.edu.kg

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ORCID: 0000-0002-4194-6682

Prof. Dr. Kırgızistan-Türkiye Manas Üniversitesi, Bişkek / Kırgızistan
cholpon.naymanova@manas.edu.kg

ORCID: 0000-0001-7828-1840

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WORLDVIEW OF THE DIGITAL AND TRADITIONAL NOMADS

ABSTRACT

In the article the new phenomenon of the 20th century – digital nomads in the correlation with historical, traditional nomads analyzed. Digital Nomads - a modern brand, conceptual innovation, symbolizes freedom without boundaries. Digital nomads are the new representatives of modern nomadism, and at the same time they are pronounced Western rationalists. In the West, the satiation with the technical achievements of culture occurred earlier, and there arose some sort of nostalgia about the natural motives. And this induced them to create some sort of illusion for themselves. This illusion exists because their way of thinking remains that of the contemporary people, nevertheless, this is some kind of a challenge. The challenge in itself, above all, at the level of personal development, and also the challenge against the society that imposes some sort of framework, making life very “tight”. Over the course of the 21st century, this brand will become even stronger, because the challenges of globalization allow finding unusual solutions. The term ‘nomad’ stands for, on the one hand, one of the ways of surviving and preserving harmony with this world, and, on the other hand, it implies approaching the world in a slightly different perspective.

Keywords: Digital nomad, Globalization, Archetype, Traditional nomad, Lifestyle, Freedom, Culture.

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DİJİTAL VE GELENEKSEL GÖÇEBELERİN DÜNYA GÖRÜŞÜ

ÖZET

Makalede yirminci yüzyılın yeni bir fenomeni olarak bilinen dijital göçebelerin tarihsel ve geleneksel göçebelerle olan ilişkisi analiz edilmektedir. Digital göçebeler sınırsız özgürlüğü simgeleyen kavramsal bir yenilik ve modern bir markadır. Dijital göçebeler, modern göçebeliğin yeni temsilcileridirler ve aynı zamanda Batılı rasyonalistler olarak kabul edilirler. Batı'da kültürün teknik başarılarının doygunluğu daha önce gerçekleşmiştir ve buna bağlı olarak, doğal olana yönelik nostalji daha önce ortaya çıkmıştır. Bu ise onları kendileri için belirli bir özgürlük yanılması yaratmaya, aynı zamanda bir tür meydan okumaya teşvik etmiştir. Kendine bir meydan okumanın yanı sıra, bir tür kalıba sokarak hayatı çok 'daraltan' topluma karşı bir meydan okumadır. 21. yüzyılda bu marka daha da güçlenecektir, çünkü küreselleşmenin meydan okumaları olağanüstü çözümler bulmada katkıda bulunmaktadır. 'Göçebe' terimi, bir yandan hayatta kalma ve bu dünya ile uyum içinde olma yollarından biri anlamına gelirken, diğer yandan dünyaya biraz farklı bir bakış açısıyla yaklaşmayı önermektedir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Dijital Göçebe, Küreselleşme, Arketip, Geleneksel Göçebe, Yaşam Tarzı, Özgürlük, Kültür.

The aim of the article is to study the concept of "digital nomad" and "traditional nomad" to determine their similarities and differences. The main focus is made on the analysis of historical nomadic culture of thinking as the archetype of nomadic culture.

In the process of several stories research of modern digital nomads from Europe and the USA and their understanding about nomad's thinking and way of life, it became clear that there is a significant difference between modern nomads and the archetype of historical nomads. It shows that the fundamental difference between digital and traditional (historical) nomads is in the contrast to the way of thinking. Western rationalism of digital nomads and contextual thinking of traditional nomads - two different understanding of the meaning of life. This is the unifying element - the dynamism in the perception of the world and the way of behavior in this world.

Currently, in social anthropology there are few researches on digital nomads. In this regard, the definition of the phenomenon of digital nomads through the relation with the archetype of historical nomads seems reasonable and relevant in terms of scientific research. A sociological survey of students about the possibilities and prospects of remote work showed that the surge of nomadism is a natural process and at the same time it is a reaction to the ratio of the technical and technological process and its impact on human development in the 21st century. At the same time, the ratio of settled and nomadic life in the history of mankind has deep roots, both in terms of coexistence and opposition in terms of the level and quality of development of cultural systems. It must be emphasized that the nomadic way of life reveals its significance in times of crisis. The emergence of nomadic nomadism in Western countries prompted a study of the essence of this phenomenon in modern times, as far as it corresponds to the challenges of historical time. The understanding of nomadism of the representatives of Western civilization was considered by the stories of the personal lives of digital nomads, and the representatives of Central Asia by the answers to the questions asked. Young Kyrgyz are the descendants of historical

nomads who had a traditional vision and way of life. In this regard, it was possible to trace the culture of thinking of traditional nomads and modern representatives of the once nomadic civilization.

It should be emphasized that in Europe and the US the phenomenon of the digital nomad is regarded as a consequence of technical and technological advances; there is objectivity. However, we are interested in the concept of the digital nomad from the view of the nomadic existence as the archetype of thinking and deeply peculiar way of life, determined the occurrence of the invariant culture system in history. At present, it makes sense to find out how the nomadic phenomenon is experiencing its renaissance, and how it relates to the way of thinking of Western man.

1. Introduction

As demonstrated by numerous studies and the emergence of the phenomenon known as ‘digital nomadism’, the phenomenon of nomadism has been undergoing a kind of renaissance in the present times. Why is it happening, and what are the similarities and differences between traditional and contemporary nomads, e.g. the location-independent workers who are referred to as digital nomads? These are people who deny the established canons. These are quite interesting people, but these are people who relate to the term of nomad in an illusionary manner. They are interested not so much in internal as much as merely external parameters. That a nomad lives the life not being tied to a geographical location. But to what extent, how deeply do they perceive the phenomenon of the nomadic way of thinking? The majority of digital nomads is simply people who want something new. There are only a few that get imbued “to the bones”. Those who immerse themselves entirely, perhaps, experience a reassessment of their values. Even if they do not become real nomads, they let it in through their external existence and, accordingly, change. At first glance, digital nomadism is a way of life, which implies movement free of any space constraints (Dutil, 2015). However, the major focus should be directed towards the particular way of thinking; thus, a lifestyle is merely its projection. What is particular about the traditional nomadic consciousness shaped in the vastness of Central Asia, and contributed to the emergence of the particular way of life, which was opposite to the sedentary lifestyle? What is the essence of nomadism? And what is the relation between nomadism as a historical phenomenon, and digital nomads projecting the modern hypostasis of nomadism? The topicality of this question is apparent given the steady increase in the number of digital nomads, and the unquenchable interest in the phenomenon of nomadism itself in the era of globalization. In this regard, archetypes of thought and culture are significant; they provide invaluable assistance in understanding the essence of the processes of identification in the present. In this sense, C. Jung was right, stating “if we cannot deny the archetypes or otherwise neutralize them, we are confronted, at every new stage in the differentiation of consciousness to which civilization attains, with the task of finding a new interpretation appropriate to this stage, in order to connect the life of the past that still exists in us with the life of the present, which threatens to slip away from it” (Jung, 2002: 91). The comparison of traditional nomadic thought (the representatives of which were located in the history of Asia and the Middle East), and contemporary Western thought (in this context, the kind of people who have chosen nomadic way of life) (Khazanov, 1984: 604) generates original interpretation. The major question investigated is the following: how do the way of thinking and the way of life of the historical and modern digital nomads intertwine?

The practical significance of the article is determined by the ability to define how the nomadic lifestyle can be adapted to modern life, high-tech age. In this regard, the new value may receive the following aspects of life: how the Western way of thinking can be paired with the nomadic lifestyle. At the same time, the notion of universal values can be extended in connection with the new manifestations

of modern life. Another aspect - the process of migration in the context of the world can get a new interpretation in the context of the relations of universal values and the phenomenon of the modern nomad.

In this case, the hermeneutic method allows not only to understand and correlate historical and digital nomads, but also understand the connection to time and ages through the prism of lifestyle.

2. Methods

Understanding the *method of W. Dilthey's hermeneutics* (Dilthey, 2004: 424) - the interaction of the individual and the world of culture. As the result, understanding the digital nomad lifestyle appears the interpretation of their way of thinking. The culture of thinking and life of digital nomad is compared with the mentality of historical nomads acting organic representatives of the nomadic lifestyle. Which features do digital nomads remind of the traditional features of historic nomads? What are their similarities and fundamental difference? Are there any similarities between the modern descendants of Western civilization - digital nomads and traditional representatives of nomadic civilization?

The analysis of Central Asian traditional culture of thinking of nomads with focus on mainly traits of nomad's character is the basis for comparison between historical and digital nomads.

It should be noted that the phenomenon of digital nomads recently designated itself in the West, a little bit more than two decades ago, digital nomads began to denote a niche in Europe as a kind of social formation. This is not an entirely studied social anthropology phenomenon. A study of the possibility and necessity of the relation of digital nomads with historical nomads is new, however, a promising field in social anthropology. In this regard, one of the sources of analysis can serve as personal stories of the representatives of the modern nomad, spread in the Internet. Few similar stories were analyzed, based on which conclusions on the habits and lifestyle of digital nomads of Europe were made. Using the method of understanding W.Dilthey, taking into account the elements of the traditional way of thinking of Western man and the novelty of the nomadic way of life of modern Europeans, conclusions on the comparability of historical and mental characteristics of the digital nomad will be drawn.

3. Literature Review

The problem is how the nomadic ways of life studied enough, but it is necessary to note two aspects: the historical development of the nomads and a separate study of digital nomads as a phenomenon of modern life. For historical nomads of Central Asia, there are interesting historical, ethnographic, philosophical studies in Kazakhstan and Kyrgyzstan. We would like to mention especially the research of N.Masanov (Masanov, 1995: 27-46) a complete picture of the genesis and evolution of nomadism. The various aspects of mentality of Central Asian nomads have been studied by researchers from Kazakhstan as E.Shakenova, K. Nurlanova, M.Auezov, M. Orynbekov, Z.Naurzbaeva, S.Akatay, D.Kshibekov (Nauryzbayeva, 2013; Lamazhaa, 2013: 99-108) Every one of them raised a particular problem in covering the specifics of mentality, culture and society.

For example, E.Shakenova focuses on the contemplative nature of the nomadic thinking. She said, that "syncretic vision of the ever-moving and changing nature of the direct living contemplation, without analysis, to develop a person's imagination, creative imagination, contributed to its approval in the world" (Shakenova, 1993: 83-84). T. Gabitov says about cultural modal personality in the Kazakh culture, which leads to the release of the mentality of Kazakh identity (Gabitov, 2012: 280). M.Orynbekov believes that in the development of Central Asia's rich culture the huge role is played by the Great Silk Road. At the same time, in spite of the specific thinking of nomads, the relationship with farmers brings some movement in the perception of the world (Orynbekov, 1994: 147-148; 158-159).

M.Auezov underlines the fact that no religion could completely conquer the heart of a nomad: "To everything there is an explanation in the ordinary consciousness of nomads in the world, and the prophet be bursting through an open door, trying to enlighten him as to truth" (Auezov, 1993: 59). Nurlanova K. marks ecological thinking of nomad, because "contemplation expresses the relationship of man and the world as a primordial organic interlinked integrity" (Nurlanova, 1993: 208).

There are also such studies about the nomadic way of life among Kyrgyz scientists. S.Abdrasulov highlights several aspects of the formation of the ontological grounds of the nomadic way of life. The symbol of the nomads seems yurt that projects a particular world view of ancient nomads (Urmanbetova, Abdrasulov, 2009: 8 -85). Such researchers as Dzhusupbekov A. and D. Ashiraliev make an emphasis on the formation of kinship as the basis of ethnic consciousness and philosophic thinking of nomads, based on Tengrianism (Dzhusupbekov, 2009:265; Ashiraliev, 2008: 230). A. Asankanov in his historical studies about the Kyrgyz, repeatedly emphasizes nomadic archetype of consciousness (Asankanov, Osmonov, 2002: 576).

Based on the study of numerous developments of nomadic culture and mentality's features, we propose a system of traditional characteristics of nomads thinking of Central Asia (Urmanbetova, 1997: 172; Urmanbetova, Abdrasulov, 2009: 86-177), the main aspects of which are set out in this article. On the basis of this system the traits of the national character were revealed; they contribute to adapt to the era of globalization, and those that inhibit the process of democratization (Urmanbetova, 2018: 291-306).

The Central Asian scientific community know about phenomenon of digital nomads, but researches were not conducted in the field of social anthropology. Objectively, the formation of the layer of digital nomads is connected with Europe and the United States, where there were the first studies. The first and the most famous monograph in this field was the book by Tsugio Makimoto and David Manners "Digital nomad", in addition to this work there are well famous Slade Michelle and Rob Dix "Being a digital nomad" (Makimoto, Manners, 2013: 236) However, in this regard, it should be noted that in this case there are studies over people's lifestyle, choosing the path of remote work. "A *Digital Nomad* is the symbol of a new lifestyle in which people are freed from constraints of time and location, thanks to the progress of mobile intelligent devices and high speed communication networks. We have observed gradual changes in the lifestyle from the traditional way to the nomadic way, notably in the past decade. It was quite common, by the turn of the 21st century, that a large number of people commuted to their workplaces, for example to their offices in the central part of big cities, at 9am or 10am either by cars or by trains every morning, and left the places in the evening at 5pm or 6pm. The regular movement of people, back and forth, creates the phenomena of heavy traffic for cars and the "rush hour" of trains. Thereby, you have more freedom from the constraints of time and location. There are three essentials to support the comfortable nomadic lifestyle, namely, an intelligent mobile terminal, a high speed communication network, and cloud computing" (Makimoto, 2013: 40-47). The emphasis is made on the lifestyle and their ability to work remotely, as well as on the quality of the gadgets. In this way of thinking is not the specifics of coming to the fore, although it is assumed that it is dynamic, mobile people who can drop imposed by society stereotypes and standards (Janeiko, 2015; Manson, 2013).

In this connection, the aim of this article is to indicate the peculiarities of the modern way of thinking of people who choose a nomadic lifestyle. The possibility of the ratio of digital nomad lifestyle and historical nomad which is the archetype of the nomadic way of life and thinking, is of particular importance. Thus, it is important to determine which of the characteristics of the historical image of nomadic thinking is in demand today, in an age of high technology and globalization (Celento, 2008:

284-291; Russell, 2013). How is nomadic culture of thinking and the modern Western mentality comparable; whether the distinction between specificity thinking nomadic and sedentary peoples erased? That is why the study of the nomadic in the context of history and the present enables to reveal new ideas for global peace.

The results of the study can be identified through the characterization of the system of traditional thinking historic nomads of Central Asia.

4. Traditional nomadic thought as conceptualized by historical nomads

The cosmic sensation in one's own 'oecumene' (Urmanbetova, 1997: 70) constituted the traditional paradigm of thinking pertaining to the Central Asian nomads. Due to the nomadic lifestyle, for traditional nomads, the idea of a journey inherently served as the basis for life. The journey was conceptualized as a conjunction between a human being and the Universe; meanwhile, Heaven and Earth served as major reference points for comprehension of life. The categories of Heaven and Earth are universal. However, in 'being' as understood by the ancient nomads, the sky personified the guardian of a human's destiny. At times, 'Tenir' (Amanaliev, 1963: 15) (the Kyrgyz word for 'Heaven') was envisioned as a supreme deity; thus, enhancing nomads' contemplation. At the same time, it should be noted that some researchers, when defining Tenir, put the emphasis not on the concept of heaven as a deity, but as an interpretation of the equivalence and equivalence of man in this world. Man enters this world as an equal. The contemplation process required rich imagination, filling in the gaps in the knowledge about existence. Human-nomad possessed high and subtle level of sensitivity, thanks to which he felt oneness with the world, nature. The contemplation was the key to understanding the being, whereas micro-world (human being) and macro-world (the Universe) intertwined into each other at the level of World-Cosmos (Phenomenon., 2007: 204). The need for change dominated nomad's consciousness, forasmuch as the constant movement from place to place were the norms of the existence, and the forms of the world cognition. Thus, a human being could easily adapt to new situations, embracing it as an extension of the uniform world. This is the reason why *dynamism* is approached here as an element of perception, which has eventually become the inherent trait of the nomadic world outlook. To a nomad, movement implies a way of thought, a lifestyle, and the major value of being, i.e. movement is substantial to the nomad's perception of the world. In this respect, due to the dynamic approach to the environment, *activism* constituted a life stance characteristic for a human-nomad. Nomad was not submitting one's own self to the world, or to the forces of nature; instead, she/he felt as an equal to them, because, indeed, she/he was a child, a creation, of this very nature, who lived in harmony with the nature's rules. Thereby, when compared to the mentality of the sessile representatives, the elements of the traditional thinking as conceptualized by nomads pose significant difference.

The dynamic display of their outlook emanated from the intrinsic sense of freedom, which organically constituted the nomads' way of thinking. Nomads were free in their thoughts, aspirations and actions; their activities were not confined to the limits of the pre-assigned behavior. To follow the logic suggesting that, from nomad's perspective, the world was an immense space unfolding the freedom of existence, it would be sequential matter-of-course to suggest that the human-nomad derived freedom of action from freedom of space, thus becoming a subject of the world. The very mode of existence – permanent nomadism – determined the perception of freedom as a given condition of life; this way, freedom of thought reflected freedom of universe. There is a deep dialectical understanding of nomadic being, his/her own destiny, and relation to this world. As said S.Abdrasulov, nomad can be called Homo Sophos, because he perceives the world not rationally, but intuitively determining the significance of what is happening, thus wisdom is in his blood. This kind of understanding was inherent to nomads, renouncing whatever canons. Freedom as natural process of self-awareness gave birth to heroic

consciousness in a nomad, a kind of militancy as the underlying character trait. The sedentary way of human existence objectively restricted by the frames of territorial and geographical space, gave rise to a completely different mode of existence in this world, and fostered different attitude to the things taking place in it. Another manifestation of freedom could be seen in nomad's tolerance to 'otherness' as a result of awareness about the benevolence of the Universe, and deep understanding about that various members are supposed to coexist in it.

The nomad's sense of the world extended to a cosmic scope implied particular sensibility towards nature (*environment-oriented way of thinking*), when nature was envisioned in the role of life-giving initial force, and continuation of human Self. Nature and human being merged into one whole, thus forming a sort of natural harmony, in which a human personified a son of the Universe. Nature's perception of the nomad was understood as spiritual; it was projecting the moral principles of human existence: the sky was associated with eternity; mountains – wisdom and mightiness; water – life itself, its source. The natural life cornerstones dominated the hierarchy of the moral values. In this sense, one may claim that the principles of nomadic life in Central Asia originally were *non-religious* per se; and for the knowledge of the essence of life, nomad did not try to resort in anything of extramundane character. Nomad adhered to the given reality: "There is an explanation to everything in the world in the everyday consciousness of a nomad, and a prophet would be bursting through an open door in an attempt to enlighten him [the nomad] regarding the 'truth'" (Auezov, 1993: 59).

The harmony of the nature-and-human relationships resulted in the respective system of cults: Earth and Water as the progenitors and source of life, and Fire as the guardian of the family hearth. The elements of the natural world constructed specific images, through the prism of which the dialogue with the world-Universe was taking place. Thus, nomadic thinking distinguished itself in its *concreteness*, because spatiality enabled localization of objects in space. In attempts to understand existence, the un-comprehended was intuitively replenished with the belief in unity of the world. Thereby, the development of '*intuitivism*' contributed to contemplativeness and speculative character.

Contemplativeness was an expression of the *philosophic* way of thinking in nomads. Nomads did not develop their own conceptual philosophical tradition, as it occurred in the East and West; the sensuous-symbolical way of world perception constituted the nomadic mode of thinking, and it did not find its place in the philosophical treatises. Surpassed by written sources for centuries, the culture of oral tradition had been rapidly developing. This unique phenomenon was captured in the epic compositions as examples of artistic thinking. Epics played a similar role to nomads as myths to sessile peoples: they were a source of spiritual culture, a historical form of world outlook at early stages of development. The fusion of real and unreal was characteristic of epics, it functioned as a reflection of nomadic consciousness, which had *mythological* quality; epics offered interpretation of a unified undifferentiated world. Epics expressed the integrity of consciousness, and memory served as a preservation criterion of the ancient nomadic culture. To quote Hegel's apt remark, "the genuinely epical event is not a single casual deed, and that consequently it is not a purely accidental happening which is related, but an action ramified into the whole of its age and national circumstances so that it can be brought before us only within an outspread world and demands the portrayal of this world in its entirety" (Hegel, 1975: 1051).

The ancient nomads' model of life was based on the traditional understanding of the world, where space prevailed over time. Hence, *spatiality* (Urmanbetova, Abdrasulov, 2009: 93) was another characteristic feature of the nomadic thinking. The world of nomads "was a spatial world, in which a human lived, and upon which he depended, it was all-powerful and all-generous, as god, as the earthly embodiment of god (Aitmatov, Lit.gazeta, November, 15). The material embodiment of the spatial

thinking of the nomad and his worship of the sky was the Kyrgyz dwelling - boz üy - the abode of everyday existence, a symbol of material culture, which combines the meaning of the World-Cosmos (Urmanbetova, 2019: 257-266). The priority of the spatial cornerstones in the nomad's consciousness of world perception did not utterly deny the time criteria of being. Nomad's understanding of time was particular; it was cyclical, and thus it was contrasted against the linear understanding adopted by the sessile peoples. The cyclical perception of the world in time was determined by the natural cycles of development. Due to sensibility to the processes occurring in nature, a nomad projected these cycles onto one's own course of life. Thus, time synthesized its hypostases, which was recognized as unity: past, present and future coexisted in impersonal space at once. And this is an extremely important characteristic of nomadic thinking, projecting its originality in the relationship between the generations.

The unity of time modes found expression in the unique feature of nomadic consciousness - self-consciousness was generated in the attempts to comprehend the spirit of past eras inhabited by past generations. This was not a sort of succession, which was common in the Western or Eastern cultures, where each generation was associated with a particular stage of history. With regard to the Central Asian culture, continuity was understood as a coherent process of constructing-and-localizing one's own 'Self,' which was supposed to be in congruent relation with the traditions of past generations. This can be described as a sort of inner spiritual kinship, which was not fading away within the course of time; on the contrary, it was strengthened by its appeal to cultures for being always up-to-date, contemporary. The continuity of generations was determined by the level of self-consciousness in a nomad; his/her link to the historical traditions of Central Asia mattered. Nomad adhered to the norms of being as upheld by ancestors; thus, the traditional thinking in nomads played a supreme role in succession of the culture of nomadic thinking, in general.

Each generation of nomads to a certain degree expanded understanding of the underlying principles of existence that constituted nomadic world outlook (Kyrgyz matrix, 2012: 31). The ancestor cult provided symbolical and spiritual guidance to a nomad who wanted to comprehend the mysteries withhold within the cosmic world perception. This way, it was believed that the ancestors stood for a lively and imperishable symbol encompassing historicity of the nomadic life; the lack of knowledge in this field led to the tragedy in the succession of nomadic culture. Traditionally, nomad was ought to know about the seven generations of his ancestors, and knowing these things was a way to appreciate one's own existence, an indication of historical co-participation. The succession of generations was made apparent in the ethnic memory, and its distinctiveness should be explained. Commemoration of ancestors, was, metaphorically speaking, a thread connecting generations; it was regarded as an identity depth criterion applied to nomadic consciousness. In regard to ethnic memory, the following is important to keep in mind: the nomad's 'I' was inseparable from the procession of 'I's of the ancestors, which was a different case in sedentary cultures emphasizing time-criterion. Contrary to the vertical historical development, the historical domain of nomads could be better described as horizontal.

Another essential characteristic of Central Asian nomadic thinking was its *symbolism* (Osmonova, 2016: 229; Sadykova, 2014: 107). The genesis of this unique way of thinking has obtained a symbolical value to it. The nomadic lifestyle, implying constant movement, contributed to the establishment of a dialogue between East and West. "The penetration of the nations of charioteers and horsemen from Central Asia—which did, in fact, reach China, India and the West and introduced the horse to the ancient civilizations—had, so he [Alfred Weber] argues, analogous consequences in all three regions. The men of these equestrian peoples came to experience, thanks to the horse, the vastness of the world. They took over the ancient civilizations by conquest. In hazards and disasters they experienced the problematic character of existence, as master-peoples they developed an heroic-tragic

consciousness that found expression in epic” (Jaspers, 2014: 16). Thus, the center of Asia became the mainspring of the world contacts. This process contributed to the expansion of history, fostering the development of the Western and Eastern thinking; meanwhile, the Central Asian nomadic consciousness was being preserved as a symbol of eternal movement, the springhead of the interaction between sessile peoples.

The historical role of the nomadic consciousness preconditioned formation of an innate *tragedy*. The tragedy of the Central Asian culture reveals its distinct fate: although nomads pioneered the idea of a journey as a way of life when the cornerstones of being were laid, and pushed forward the dialogue between East and West, nevertheless, the nomadic civilization itself remained for many centuries unseen and unexplored. This way, the criteria of this distinct mode of thought manifested in a symbolical sense; in this state of things unveils itself the tragedy of the nomadic culture of Central Asia, which, at the same time, constitutes its unique quality. This tragedy of the Central Asian cultural development was expressed, preserved and passed on in the epical heroic consciousness.

The symbolism also penetrated the world of human relations: the beginning of life was associated with the image of a particular animal. It was a manifestation of historical memory of the once undivided unity of a nomad with nature. This fundamental feature of the nomadic way of thinking received ambivalent interpretation in both, Eastern and Western cultures, which relied on the stereotypical patterns of thinking inherent to them. However, the relation between human and nature was less apparent, less direct in these culture-(Urmanbetova, 2019: 421-430).

Nomadic culture implied a certain coexistence of humans and animals within the unified natural world. The symbolism inherent to nomadic thinking was also exemplified by ancestors (Arbaces) (Amanaliev, 1963: 29; Valihanov, 1958: 129; Abramzon, 1946: 53), who had been serving as symbols of stability and continuity of generations for a long while. The instinct of self-preservation in nomads ordained construction of cultural traditions to preserve the distinctive ‘container’ of the ethnic memory, which gained symbolical significance within the course of time. This contributed to the preservation of the archetype of the nomadic consciousness passed on generations by the descendants of the Central Asian culture.

Another distinctive feature of the nomadic way of thinking in Central Asia that should be addressed here is *contextualism*, i.e. awareness of the context in which one’s own self is being located. This kind of self-awareness was regarded as something that had been already predetermined by the way of existence – constant movement in the wild nature setting required unity of a human with fellow tribe members, because one could hardly manage to withstand the hardships and adversities of nature being left on his/her own. In the age of antiquity, this feature played an overly positive role, thus promoting cohesion among nomads in the difficult moments of life. The feeling of belonging to the context of a tribe remained innate to nomadic consciousness for a long period of time afterwards.

In light of demand and practical capacity, the aforementioned characteristics of nomadic thinking led to the possibility of creating a peculiar unaltered cultural model, which served as a basis for—and became an archetype of—a fundamentally different way of life and perception of life. Thus, nomadism in the history of mankind’s origin and development is an essentially unique phenomenon, demonstrating specific characteristics.

5. Development Stages of Central Asia: from Nomadic to Sessile Lifestyle

Certain characteristics of the traditional nomadic thinking determined the emergence and development of a particular mentality among the representatives of Central Asia, which became a

historic area of ancient nomads (Urmanbetova, 2021: 22-29). When compared to the history of East and West, the Central Asia with its unique history has undergone the periods of incoherence because the tradition of the nomadic culture has not been originally preserved. This suggests that the characteristics of the archetype of the Central Asian way of thinking have been preserved on a subconscious level. The same processes at work can be traced in the structures of a variety of other ethnic cultures in Central Asia, dating back to the ancient Turkic tribes inhabiting this area. At the core of the traditional world outlook there is the archetypal way of thinking, which is essential to the existence of Central Asian culture. The nomadic ancestors made the psychic mindset salient, thus shaping the traditional mentality over historical time, which became a cornerstone of national character. Accordingly, the traditional mentality is fundamental to the formation of national consciousness. The cultural system underwent significant changes because of the transition to sessile lifestyle; the values constituting the nomadic culture were reconsidered, however, the most functional ones remained. The latter prevailed in the consciousness of the peoples who were highly aware of their unity with the nomadic archetype. This natural process of self-awareness within the new conditions of life led to the mutual enrichment of principles constituting the nomadic and settled world outlooks, and this contributed to *syncretism* in thinking.

The entry into the Soviet epoch of development led to reorientation of the nomadic way of thinking, which had been eventually superseded by the fusion of the Eastern and some Western characteristics of consciousness. The traditional world outlook did not perish entirely, certain manifestations were preserved in the form of national traditions and customs; however, the major criterion constituting the nomadic outlook on the world was pushed to the level of the subconscious. The course of further development placed significant value on the principles constituting the sessile culture; those received obsolete status (Stamova, Soorbekova, 2011: 90-124).

The next leap in the traditional cultural system occurred with the acquisition of sovereignty by the Central Asian republics. This process created a crisis in the nations' self-determination, accompanying the process of independent development up to the present time. The process of sovereignty raised the issue of the revival of the Central Asian cultural archetype. The Central Asia as a single territorial and geopolitical region manifested itself in the process of the republics' self-development. At the national level, there occurred the necessity in re-interpretation of the past socio-cultural experience. In contemporary scholarship, the emphasis is made on studying the specifics of mentality. The surge of national consciousness contributed to the revival of the traditional cultural values. Simultaneously, another trend of development persisted: the process of globalization promoted the penetration and 'absolutization' of the universal values. In the context of this situation, national, regional and global interest become intertwined. The processes of modernization also have an impact on the cultural system, and its expression in terms of values. In its turn, the public system reflects the contradictions of the so-called transitional period. Accordingly, certain parameters of the nomadic mentality remain on a subconscious level today. They manifest themselves in the ability to adapt to changing conditions of life relatively easier; and this has to do with the previously mentioned dynamism of nomadic thought coupled with the nomad's inclination to take an active role in the perception and the development of their new world. However, it should be noted that the modern descendants of nomads are no longer representatives of the classic nomadic way of thinking. The contemporary way of life was foreordained by the sessile way of existence together with the invasion of the global stereotypes and universal values; today, the lifestyle of the nomads' descendants negates the relevance of some of the features of the traditional nomadic thinking. In addition to that, the history itself repeatedly reaches the points when updates of the traditional system of thinking becomes a necessity. Affirmations about

globalization entering the phase of post-globalization highlights the complexity of this development, and its contradictory nature. Along with the incitement of unification, globalization deepens the processes of identification. In such state of things, the archetypes of thinking forcefully come to the surface of consciousness, revealing their power and validity, and promising the possibility of a new 'push' towards better understanding of one's own culture and being. Thus, nomadism, which represents one of the archetypes of thinking and culture, receives an opportunity of reinterpretation within the given cultural systems (Baybosunov, 2012: 142-152; Urmanbetova et al., 2019: 54-84).

The particular aspect of nomadism contributing to its popularization today manifests itself in the phenomenon of digital nomadism, which has a lot to do with the endless migration sweeping the world as a way of human existence – the consequence of globalization.

6. Digital nomads in relation to the historical nomads

The destiny of nomads is to play a role in the critical periods in the development of human civilization, when the sedentary type of existence in some way exhausts its potential. In modern times, the openness of the world, due to globalization with its destruction of generally accepted boundaries and involvement in the concept of a "one world", has pushed forward the understanding of digital nomadism as the most modern way of human existence in general. This means that with the dominance of sedentary life in the refraction of certain types of civilization and systems of culture, nomadism again becomes a kind of unifying principle of all cultures, peoples, and states. This is the response of man to the challenge of history and time. This is one of the ways, on the one hand, to survive and not to lose harmony with this world, and on the other hand, to present the world in a slightly different perspective. Modernity is another example, when in the era of globalization as a relatively new trend of being, nomadism once again declared itself as a kind of unique phenomenon that makes sense to copy. This means that the phenomenon of nomadism at the subconscious level is capable of producing some shocks in history.

Digital nomads comprise a solely modern-day phenomenon, which has become of profound current interest and gained importance in Europe and the U.S., i.e. concentrated in the Western world. On the one hand, the very name "digital nomads" signifies technological determinism of this phenomenon, suggesting the high level of the current world civilization development. This phenomenon would be unimaginable without the advances in the digital technologies; hence, this is phenomenon of the world of reason. On the other hand, the combination of the Western way of thinking with conscious preference for nomadic way of existence in the modern times suggests ambivalent interpretation of the term "digital nomads" (Urmanbetova, 2017: 262-271).

Technological achievements of the human civilization allow the contemporaries take advantage of freedom as a way of existence: when it comes to work disposal, the opportunity of remote work implies that an individual has more freedom to decide (Leffel, 2014; Hart, 2015). Hence, in regard to space and time, the major criteria of being, the contemporary world appears in a slightly different perspective. The pace of time is fast; as a result, the time has become regarded as both, something given and luxury. Previously enclosed and framed, space became perceived as open. At the present time, the borders between states lost their significance thanks to the emergence of the Internet, and the Internet-related technological developments. The concept of the virtual space gained significance because it contributed to the emergence of a particular world. This implied that time and space as the criteria of human existence enabled the possibility of a new approach to their understanding, perception, and function. In this regard, digital nomad projects an up-to-date vision of nomadism-phenomenon by adopting the metaphor which refers to freedom, i.e. it can be viewed as a contemporary brand, an innovative concept, a symbol applied to designate freedom without limits. This is a product of

globalization, which can be approached as a universal value “packaged” as contemporary nomadism. And that was the first interpretation of the term “digital nomads”.

Along with this interpretation, there exists the second, which penetrates deeper into the essence of nomadism. According to this interpretation, digital nomad is someone who chooses freedom not merely for the sake of flexible allocation of time, but also for a deeper purpose – the opportunity to perceive this world and one’s own place within it in a quite different light, i.e. nomadism as a way of thinking in addition to the way of life. In this sense, how does digital nomad relate to the classical nomad? To what extent does this metaphor correspond to the archetypical historical phenomenon?

Dynamism is the most acclaimed quality in the appropriated image of a nomad, interpreted as constant movement, roaming entity. Thus, mobility alters itself from the characteristic of a contemporary man into an inherent characteristic of the individual’s essence. The second characteristics of such kind of freedom without limits is the preference in favor of space that is non-oppressive, similar to time, towards the human being’s consciousness. Such understanding of freedom allows comparative approach to a digital nomad, a contemporary representative of the technical and technological civilization, with the historical one respectively, i.e. the traditional nomad whose approach to the perception and understanding of the world is very distinctive.

However, parallels that can be drawn between the preferences of the traditional and contemporary nomads do not necessarily signify absolute approximation of the carriers sharing similar characteristics. What distinguishes the contemporary digital nomad from the traditional one? The lack of nomadic thinking integrity: despite their presence, certain nomadic characteristics, such as the nomadic way of thinking and way of life, in the contemporary representatives of the Western world do not constitute the perception of nomadism as the philosophy of life. Why is integrity important? Because one can feel a nomad only in a certain systematization of thought, i.e. when despite understanding of freedom as the supreme values of being, a nomad retains such qualities of thinking as contemplativeness, intuitiveness, spatiality, symbolism, etc. Such integrity of thinking is at the core of invariant model of behavior. In this case, all these qualities become natural and functional, rather than superficial.

To the most degree digital nomads are representatives of the West pertaining Western mentality inherent to them, with a strongly pronounced rationalism. Most of them are quite rational people. The digital nomad perceives rules as the highest level of rationality. That is why the digital nomad is a consequence of Homo sapiens. We suggest that their rationality manifests itself in their deliberate search for a life stance for some kind of relief, escape from imposed stereotypes and standards. Their goal lies in the alteration of life quality; this means that certain burdens related to life organization are pushed into the background. Wherein, obtainment of one’s own “Self” takes place not in the context of the accepted norms, but rather in spite of them. Speaking of the history of traditional nomads, such kind of rationalism was inappropriate to them; traditional nomads were more organic to the nature that “enveloped” them. Bearing this in mind, the contemporary Western nomads appear as adopting the idealized version of the metaphor of nomadism, which offers new rhythm and originality to the contemporary life.

In fact, a closer look at the comparisons drawn between the traditional nomadic and Western ways of thinking can serve as a point of departure for the analysis of the opposition of these parameters. The major characteristics of the Western way of thinking are: anthropocentrism (as opposed to the nomadic cosmocentrism), as a result of which technological thinking subduing nature (in opposition to the organic environmental susceptibility) comes to foreground; the prevalence of the timeline-oriented criteria of existence (as opposed to the spatiality-oriented mentality inherent to nomads), and the

perception of time is linear (rather than cyclic as perceived by traditional nomads); theoretical thinking (as opposed to contemplation and intuition); egoism and pragmatism (as opposed to contextuality), rationality (as opposed to emotional irrationality); abstractedness (as opposed to concreteness); vertical continuity constituted by the vertical hierarchy of memories (as opposed to horizontal); the culture of rights as opposed to tribalism.

Dynamism with accompanying easiness in perception of changes taking place in the world, is the only aspect uniting nomadic Central-Asian and Western ways of thinking. However, digital nomads' adoption of freedom of movement does not imply acceptance of a particular spiritual perception, enlightenment present in true nomads. Only a few people are able to embrace the values of this lifestyle fully, and comprehend over time the distinctiveness of its spirit, which "refills" them anew. Digital nomads are a product of globalization with its universal values and virtual space. Spatial limits of the real world get blurred in the context of technological progress; hence, the world becomes open space, accessible to everyone, and, as a consequence, desired. The world without borders implies freedom; however, the perception of such freedom might turn out to be an illusion of sort. In this sense the contemporary nomads, as already explained, simply adopt the metaphor of nomadism, which serves the new purpose of discovering one's own "Self" in the context of the dynamically changing world. A comparison drawn between the ways of thinking of settled and nomadic civilizations suggests that the West (categorized as a traditionally sessile civilization type) does not offer natural conditions pertinent to nomadism. Thus, the conscious choice of the nomadic way of life in modern times does not imply the primordially natural perception of the world and life; contrary to the situation of historical nomads it entails no harmonious coexistence of a human and nature. This seems to be the fundamental difference between digital and historical nomads. Despite this difference, the western individual's pursuit of adopting nomadic lifestyle as a way of existence—by putting one's own self into the state of being-in-between, and constant movement—shows that such an option is conceived as natural and organic in the era of globalization as a consequence of a high level of technological progress.

7. Conclusion

Determined by globalization with its destruction of common borders and its involvement into the construction of a "unified world," the openness of the contemporary world, implies understanding of nomadism as the most up-to-date way of human existence, in general. This means that in the set of circumstances when the dominant sessile way of existence becomes deciphered through the lenses of the certain types of civilization and cultural systems, nomadism acquires the role of a unifying foundation for all cultures, states, and peoples. This is a human's response to the challenge of history and time, i.e. the indication of deeper understanding of nomadism as a way of life. In this case, nomadism is but one of the ways, on the one hand, to survive and preserve the harmony with this world; and on the other hand, this is an attempt to see the world in a slightly different perspective. In this regard, it should be noted that nomadism is destined to play a role in the particular periods of history. History itself created this distinctive feature: when the East and West were undergoing the period of formation, and were practically unknown to each other, nomads filled the roles of informants communicating to the West and East about each other's existence. Thus, nomads contributed to the formation of world history. In the end of the twentieth century, the socio-cultural boom took place because of destruction of the enormous state, an empire; these conditions gave rise to chaos. In these circumstances, the concept of a nomad re-surfaced again, serving the purpose of some sort of bridge connecting different cultural worlds. That explains the "hype" around this term; no wonder it is being commercialized, because we are living in the age of technological determinism: we want to package everything and lay out for sale to produce profit. Nevertheless, we should keep the uniqueness of this phenomenon in sight: nomadism

did not perish within the course of history; on the contrary, it came to surface again with renewed vigor. And in this lies the huge potential, enormous power of nomadism as a phenomenon.

We believe that over the course of the 21st century, this brand will become even stronger, because the challenges of globalization allow finding unusual solutions. The term ‘nomad’ stands for, on the one hand, one of the ways of surviving and preserving harmony with this world, and, on the other hand, it implies approaching the world in a slightly different perspective. Settled civilizations are used to a ‘typical’ perspective of perception, and a fresh flow is essential for them. Nomad became precisely that fresh breath of air for the West and even for the East. The potential of this archetype can be explained with a cocoon metaphor: at some point it [the archetype] revealed all its strength, then it curled into itself, and, invisible to anyone, it rolled around like a small sphere, it might have been kicked around here and there, but suddenly it found itself in a whirlwind again. We are now at the start of this swirl that will unfold, and the amplitude will increase accordingly. N.Berdyaev spoke knowingly that this century of historic catastrophes is nevertheless temporary (Berdyaev, 1990: 5). Sooner or later, stability will set in again, and the nomadic archetype and brand will, again, curl themselves into a cocoon. It will wait for its next historical hour. And this is the advantage of this archetype of thinking that makes it different from the respected West and East, which, in their turn, are ‘culturological’ stereotypes; the latter are fundamental, but they always depend on their stability, they crave for continuity. In case of the history of nomads, its discontinuity is very interesting. It seems to us that there are a lot of interesting things ahead of us: in the sense of re-discovering the sense of this nomadic type, and the application of the term in the entirely various areas.

Research of digital nomad in relation to historical archetypes nomads will continue to reflect contemporary nomadic aspect in the world of global migration. In this regard, it makes sense to designate a point of contact between researchers and Central Asia and the Western and European studies. If Western researchers reveal features of the digital nomad lifestyle, the Central Asian scholars in their works reflect the specific mindset of historical nomads. Perhaps a combination of the characteristics of nomadic thinking and modern representatives of the global world reveals a new facet of human thinking of the 21st century.

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